

UCL

Design and discussion of a (reusable) Sustainability Dashboard of Open Source Tools

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**CENTRE FOR ADVANCED
RESEARCH COMPUTING**

Get your phones/laptops ready:

We will use [menti.com](https://www.menti.com) & QR codes for Interactive surveying

An RSE collaboration between **Scikit-Surgery**

[Read The Docs](#)

Library of tools for surgical navigation,
actively developed by researchers in
**Wellcome / EPSRC Centre for
Interventional and Surgical Sciences
(WEISS)**

Scikit-Surgery libraries implements a family of compact, orthogonal, libraries accompanied by robust testing, documentation, and quality control. Scikit-Surgery libraries can be rapidly assembled into testable clinical applications and subsequently translated to production software without the need for software reimplementations.

Getting started:

Wondering which library is suitable for your job and how to use it? Check out the list of included libraries, relevant documentation and demo tutorials.

Packages:

Library	Purpose
scikit-surgerycore	Algorithms/tools common to all scikit-surgery packages. Read more...
scikit-surgeryimage	Image processing algorithms using OpenCV. Read more...
scikit-surgeryvtk	Implements VTK functionality for IGS applications. Read more...
scikit-surgeryutils	Example applications/utilities. Read more...

and UCL's Advanced Center for Research Computing

Guided by fundamental principles of Open Source Software and Collaboration

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Open Source Software Sustainability Funding Call

Project: Open-source tools for Encouraging Sustainability in Diverse Multi-Library Projects

As Scikit-Surgery,

“we have developed a single sustainability dashboard ... that pulls together some of the publicly available measures of software sustainability onto a single dynamic webpage”

- keeping track of their (evolving) research community
- fundraising

The existing sustainability dashboard

deployed in <https://scikit-surgery.github.io/scikit-surgery-stats/>

scikitsurgery library status

Library	Total Weeks Up	Latest Release Date	CI Status	Docs	Coverage	Lines of Code	Downloads with Mirror	Stars	Forks	Watchers	Contributors	Package Health	v
scikit-surgeryimac	Weeks Up 242	Last Release 2022-03-22	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 93%	LOC 5372	downloads 988	Stars 0	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 4	package health 44/100	
scikit-surgerycore	Weeks Up 241	Last Release 2022-02-08	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 98%	LOC 3382	downloads 75k	Stars 4	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 6	package health 44/100	
scikit-surgeryoverlays	Weeks Up 238	Last Release 2019-01-02	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs unknown	coverage unknown		downloads 9k					package health 36/100	
scikit-surgeryvideotools	Weeks Up 238	Last Release 2018-12-23	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs unknown	coverage unknown		downloads 5k					package health 36/100	
scikit-surgeryvtk	Weeks Up 235	Last Release 2023-06-20	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 91%	LOC 6269	downloads 103k	Stars 16	Forks 4	Watchers 4	Contrib 7	package health 66/100	
ndcube	Weeks Up 234	Last Release 2023-01-11	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs unknown	coverage unknown	LOC 7268	downloads 159k	Stars 2	Forks 2	Watchers 2	Contrib 12	package health 56/100	
scikit-surgeryndtracker	Weeks Up 234	Last Release 2023-04-19	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 61%	LOC 2026	downloads 35k	Stars 29	Forks 10	Watchers 4	Contrib 7	package health 61/100	
scikit-surgeryutils	Weeks Up 232	Last Release 2023-06-22	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 40%	LOC 2372	downloads 42k	Stars 3	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 5	package health 69/100	
scikit-surgerypdcpp	Weeks Up 227	Last Release 2020-06-13	CI Status build passing	docs missing	coverage unknown	LOC 14407	downloads 118k	Stars 2	Forks 0	Watchers 6	Contrib 2	package health 39/100	
OMakeCatchTemplate	Weeks Up 227	Last Release 2019-03-05	CI Status build passing	docs unknown	coverage unknown	LOC 13669	downloads 175k	Stars 25	Forks 12	Watchers 4	Contrib 4	package health 39/100	
scikit-surgeryopenicpp	Weeks Up 227	Last Release 2020-06-09	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs unknown	coverage unknown	LOC 13274	downloads 185k	Stars 0	Forks 3	Watchers 6	Contrib 2	package health 39/100	
scikit-surgerybtk	Weeks Up 225	Last Release 2022-03-01	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 42%	LOC 2298	downloads 13k	Stars 0	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 2	package health 52/100	
scikit-surgeryyasttracker	Weeks Up 223	Last Release 2023-04-27	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 100%	LOC 2673	downloads 29k	Stars 2	Forks 0	Watchers 4	Contrib 3	package health 64/100	
scikit-surgerydialmc	Weeks Up 218	Last Release 2020-10-06	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage unknown	LOC 2618	downloads 5k					package health 38/100	
scikit-surgery-sphere-fitting	Weeks Up 216	Last Release 2021-07-27	CI Status ci.yml no status	docs passing	coverage 100%	LOC 1593	downloads 7k	Stars 1	Forks 0	Watchers 1	Contrib 1	package health 42/100	
scikit-surgeryyastosimulator	Weeks Up 215	Last Release 2021-07-21	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs unknown	coverage 100%		downloads 4k	Stars repo not found	Forks repo not found	Watchers repo not found	Contrib 3	package health 43/100	
scikit-surgeryspeck	Weeks Up 207	Last Release 2022-03-01	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 41%	LOC 1706	downloads 17k	Stars 0	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 5	package health 46/100	
mappysync	Weeks Up 206	Last Release 2023-03-28	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 100%	LOC 2121	downloads 15k	Stars 10	Forks 2	Watchers 4	Contrib 3	package health 58/100	
scikit-surgery-evaluation	Weeks Up 198	Last Release 2022-03-02	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 81%	LOC 1928	downloads 8k	Stars 0	Forks 1	Watchers 2	Contrib 2	package health 46/100	
scikit-surgerytrackersvalidation	Weeks Up 186	Last Release 2022-02-24	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 100%	LOC 2418	downloads 9k	Stars 1	Forks 0	Watchers 2	Contrib 1	package health 46/100	
scikit-surgeryif	Weeks Up 175	Last Release 2022-03-22	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 17%	LOC 2384	downloads 5k	Stars 1	Forks 0	Watchers 4	Contrib 5	package health 46/100	
scikit-surgerycalibration	Weeks Up 167	Last Release 2023-02-25	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 84%	LOC 5658	downloads 32k	Stars 5	Forks 1	Watchers 3	Contrib 4	package health 60/100	
scikit-surgeryboard	Weeks Up 167	Last Release 2023-06-28	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 89%	LOC 2924	downloads 9k	Stars 5	Forks 1	Watchers 4	Contrib 6	package health 66/100	
scikit-surgerygata	Weeks Up 161	Last Release 2022-03-24											
scikit-surgeryfren	Weeks Up 160	Last Release 2022-01-26	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 93%	LOC 3928	downloads 16k	Stars 2	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 1	package health 44/100	
scikit-surgerysysfacematch	Weeks Up 160	Last Release 2020-10-22	CI Status ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 91%	LOC 2710	downloads 16k	Stars 1	Forks 0	Watchers 2	Contrib 2	package health 42/100	

Open-source tools for Encouraging Sustainability in Diverse Multi-Library Projects

As ARC + Scikit-Surgery:

set of goals to make it more

- Active : CI/CD
- Useful : for researchers, what is “sustainability” and which metrics best capture this?
- Wide-reaching : how can researchers/RSEs outside of this domain use this dashboard as an example?

This is why... **we need insights from the research software community**

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The existing sustainability dashboard deployed in <https://scikit-surgery.github.io/scikit-surgery-stats/>

scikitsurgery library status

Library	Total Weeks Up	Latest Release Date	CI Status	Docs	Coverage	Lines of Code	Downloads with Mirror	Stars	Forks	Watchers	Contributors	Package Health	N
0 scikit-surgery-magn	Weeks Up 242	Last Release 2022-03-25	ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 93%	LOC 5372	downloads 98k	Stars 0	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 4	package health 44/100	
1 scikit-surgery-core	Weeks Up 241	Last Release 2022-02-06	ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 98%	LOC 3382	downloads 75k	Stars 4	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 6	package health 44/100	
2 scikit-surgery-vertax	Weeks Up 238	Last Release 2019-01-02	CI Status	docs unknown	coverage unknown		downloads 9k					package health 36/100	
3 scikit-surgery-wideoutlet	Weeks Up 238	Last Release 2018-12-23	CI Status	docs unknown	coverage unknown		downloads 5k					package health 36/100	
4 scikit-surgery-ytk	Weeks Up 235	Last Release 2023-06-20	ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 91%	LOC 6269	downloads 30k	Stars 16	Forks 4	Watchers 4	Contrib 7	package health 66/100	
5 ndcapp	Weeks Up 234	Last Release 2023-01-11	ci.yml passing	docs unknown	coverage unknown	LOC 7268	downloads 15k	Stars 2	Forks 2	Watchers 2	Contrib 12	package health 56/100	
6 scikit-surgery-ditracker	Weeks Up 234	Last Release 2023-04-19	ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 61%	LOC 2026	downloads 35k	Stars 29	Forks 10	Watchers 4	Contrib 7	package health 61/100	
7 scikit-surgery-ytdis	Weeks Up 232	Last Release 2023-06-22	ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 40%	LOC 2372	downloads 42k	Stars 3	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 5	package health 69/100	
8 scikit-surgery-dpp	Weeks Up 227	Last Release 2020-06-13	build passing	docs failing	coverage unknown	LOC 14407	downloads 13k	Stars 2	Forks 0	Watchers 6	Contrib 2	package health 39/100	
9 Chalk-CatchTemplate	Weeks Up 227	Last Release 2019-03-05	build passing	docs unknown	coverage unknown	LOC 13669	downloads 17k	Stars 25	Forks 12	Watchers 4	Contrib 4	package health 39/100	
10 scikit-surgery-ops-vcpp	Weeks Up 227	Last Release 2020-06-09	CI Status	docs unknown	coverage unknown	LOC 13274	downloads 10k	Stars 0	Forks 3	Watchers 6	Contrib 2	package health 39/100	
11 scikit-surgery-ik	Weeks Up 225	Last Release 2022-03-01	ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 42%	LOC 2258	downloads 13k	Stars 0	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 2	package health 52/100	
12 scikit-surgery-arcotracker	Weeks Up 223	Last Release 2023-04-27	ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 100%	LOC 2673	downloads 29k	Stars 2	Forks 0	Watchers 4	Contrib 3	package health 64/100	
13 scikit-surgery-dynamic	Weeks Up 218	Last Release 2020-10-06	CI Status	docs passing	coverage unknown	LOC 2018	downloads 5k					package health 36/100	
14 scikit-surgery-sphere-fitting	Weeks Up 216	Last Release 2021-07-27	ci.yml no status	docs passing	coverage 100%	LOC 1593	downloads 7k	Stars 1	Forks 0	Watchers 1	Contrib 1	package health 42/100	
15 scikit-surgery-tomosimulator	Weeks Up 215	Last Release 2023-07-21	ci.yml passing	docs unknown	coverage 100%		downloads 4k	Stars repo not found	Forks repo not found	Watchers repo not found	Contrib 3	package health 43/100	
16 scikit-surgery-speech	Weeks Up 207	Last Release 2022-03-01	ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 41%	LOC 1706	downloads 1k	Stars 0	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 5	package health 46/100	
17 mappysync	Weeks Up 206	Last Release 2023-03-28	ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 100%	LOC 2121	downloads 1k	Stars 10	Forks 2	Watchers 4	Contrib 3	package health 58/100	
18 scikit-surgery-evaluation	Weeks Up 186	Last Release 2022-03-02	ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 51%	LOC 1928	downloads 8k	Stars 0	Forks 1	Watchers 2	Contrib 2	package health 46/100	
19 scikit-surgery-tracker-visualizations	Weeks Up 186	Last Release 2022-02-24	ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 100%	LOC 2418	downloads 9k	Stars 1	Forks 0	Watchers 2	Contrib 1	package health 46/100	
20 scikit-surgery-rl	Weeks Up 175	Last Release 2023-03-22	ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 17%	LOC 2394	downloads 5k	Stars 1	Forks 0	Watchers 4	Contrib 5	package health 46/100	
21 scikit-surgery-calibration	Weeks Up 167	Last Release 2023-02-22	ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 94%	LOC 5658	downloads 32k	Stars 5	Forks 1	Watchers 3	Contrib 4	package health 60/100	
22 scikit-surgery-band	Weeks Up 167	Last Release 2023-06-28	ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 89%	LOC 2924	downloads 9k	Stars 5	Forks 1	Watchers 4	Contrib 6	package health 66/100	
23 scikit-surgery-goisp	Weeks Up 161	Last Release 2022-03-24											
24 scikit-surgery-vrind	Weeks Up 160	Last Release 2022-01-26	ci.yml passing	docs passing	coverage 73%	LOC 3928	downloads 3k	Stars 2	Forks 0	Watchers 3	Contrib 1	package health 44/100	
25 scikit-surgery-surface-matching	Weeks Up 160	Last Release 2020-10-22	CI Status	docs passing	coverage 91%	LOC 2710	downloads 3k	Stars 1	Forks 0	Watchers 2	Contrib 2	package health 42/100	

Metrics displayed in our dashboard

Metrics (default)	Source	Definition
Total weeks up	Github Repo	Created date
Last Update Date	Github Repo	Last activity in default branch
Lines of Code	Github Repo + cloc tool	Total lines of code in latest version of default branch
Stars	Github Repo	
Forks	Github Repo	
Watchers	Github Repo	
Contributors	Github Repo	

Metrics displayed in our dashboard

Metrics (optional: based on availability)	Source	Definition
CI Status	PyPI.org ->	Latest GHA status from <code>.github/workflows</code>
Docs	PyPI.org ->	Docs coverage badge from <code>readthedocs.org</code>
Coverage	PyPI.org ->	Coverage stats from <code>coveralls.io</code>
Downloads with Mirror	PyPI.org ->	stats from <code>pepy.tech</code>
Package Health	PyPI.org ->	definition from <code>snky.io/advisor</code> : Not described but there a table that suggests it is a combined score of “security” + “popularity” + “maintenance” + “community”
Maintainability	PyPI.org ->	Definition from <code>codeclimate.org</code> : Maintainability is an estimate of technical debt in the repo based on a standardized 10-point assessment of Duplication, Cyclomatic Complexity, Cognitive Complexity, and structural issues.”

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Our simple deployment strategy


```
schedule:  
- cron: '0 */12 * * *' # Redeploy the dashboard every 12 hours
```

To : Github-pages of the organisation,

CI : embedded within a Github-Action, cron scheduled

Triggers a set of python scripts that pull & format data and generate the html's of dashboard

Using Jameslves/

GitHub Pages

Dashboard Template (in dev) (tell us if there are others!)

Cookieninja - A Cookiecutter Fork

pypi v1.0.0 python 3.7 | 3.8 | 3.9 | 3.10 CI/CD Tests passing codecov 100% docs passing Scrutinizer 9.14

A command-line utility that creates projects from `cookiecutters` (project templates), e.g. creating a Python package project from a Python package project template.

Includes

- Analysis pipeline
- Dashboard html files
- Github Action to deploy to Pages

Needed

- Github Permissions
- target base Python library ex. `astropy` , `nif`

(detailed steps in documentation, in UK RSE conference)

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Take-away and thank you

- Sustainability dashboards can add value to open source research
- Metrics to benchmark sustainability are varied and can be hard to define
- We propose a template for users to create their dashboards, for which we will hold a **workshop in the upcoming UK RSE conference**

Find me in RSE slack/
yaamur.idil.ozdemir@ucl.ac.uk
for questions

Huge thank you to my collaborators,
Dr. Miguel Xochicale and Dr. Stephen Thompson; and my colleagues at UCL ARC

Questions we are interested in

Some questions we are interested in:

- What metrics could be better improved or removed in the current dashboard?
- Styling suggestions?
- Template: how likely would you be to use it?
- What are things you would change in the template if you were to use it?

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Share your thoughts on the scikit-
surgery dashboard!

